

A Lagrangian Particle Model to study Atmospheric Dynamics: the LPDMX

Yang Tian^{1,*}, Giuseppe Torri^{2,*}, and Zhiming Kuang^{3,4}

¹National Center for Atmospheric Research, Boulder, USA

²Department of Atmospheric Sciences, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa, Honolulu, USA

³Department of Earth and Planetary Sciences, Harvard University, Cambridge, USA

⁴John Paulson School of Engineering and Applied Sciences, Harvard University, Cambridge, USA

Correspondence: Yang Tian (ytian@ucar.edu)

Abstract. High-resolution large eddy simulations or cloud resolving models are widely used nowadays to understand the underlying processes in complex atmospheric flows. Those models adopt an Eulerian perspective to solve high-pass filtered Navier-Stokes equations, and are useful in providing detailed statistics of the processes of interest. While versatile in addressing issues that involve turbulence and clouds, the Eulerian perspective cannot explicitly track material exchange and transport, as well as the evolutionary history of those processes, which can be better addressed from a Lagrangian perspective. In this work, we designed a Lagrangian Particle Dispersion Model (LPDMX) that can be run online with a LES/CRM model, which further expand their capacity through providing a Lagrangian view of turbulent activities.

1 Introduction

Numerical models are an invaluable tool in complex sciences, where either the mathematical form of the equations governing a system or complicated boundary conditions make it impossible to obtain analytical solutions. In the study of the Earth's atmosphere, numerical models have been applied successfully in many contexts (Stohl and Trickl, 1999; Emanuel et al., 2008; Brioude et al., 2013; Angevine et al., 2013; Torri et al., 2015; Tian and Kuang, 2016; Knutson et al., 2016; Ádám Leelöšsy et al., 2017). For example, they have contributed to the development of weather forecasting (Powers, 2007; Skamarock et al., 2008; Bre, 2013; Flato et al., 2013; Schwartz et al., 2015; Seneviratne et al., 2016), an effort that was considered almost impossible before computers were invented; Global Climate Models (GCMs) are now commonly utilized to make predictions as to how the Earth's climate will evolve in the next century (Spiegelhalter et al., 2008; Sokolov et al., 2009; Sherwood and Huber, 2013; Wuebbles et al., 2018). Over the last few decades, a host of models have been built and distributed that allow studying the atmosphere at different scales and with varying degree of realism.

The models used in the study of atmospheric convection are usually Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) models, inherited from computational fluid dynamics and capable of resolving turbulence down to the inertial sub-range, or Cloud-Resolving Models (CRMs), typically of a coarser resolution than LES models and designed specifically to study cloud-related processes that involve phase changes of water (Siebesma et al., 2003). Both types of models adopt an Eulerian perspective and solve high-pass filtered Navier-Stokes, using parameterizations to represent sub-grid scale turbulent, microphysical, and radiation processes.

While the approach offered by these kinds of models is very versatile and has led to considerable progress in our understanding of many atmospheric phenomena (Guichard and Couvreur, 2017), many problems can be better addressed by using a Lagrangian perspective.

One example where Lagrangian techniques have been widely utilized is the study of the transport and mixing of chemical species in the atmosphere (Wohltmann and Rex, 2009). In these types of studies, a Lagrangian particle is interpreted as a molecule of a chemical species and, using local winds provided, for example, by an Eulerian model, its position is either integrated in the future or in the past. Lagrangian models can better represent filament-like structures because, compared to Eulerian models, they show less diffusion (Reithmeier and Sausen, 2002; Cassiani et al., 2016; Pisso et al., 2019). Lagrangian methods have also been used in the study of severe weather: for example, the release of a limited number of Lagrangian trajectories in a certain area of a supercell storm can help understand sources of vorticity or the origin of downdraft air (Ziegler, 2013). Considering the complex structure of supercell storms, the ability to follow a family of trajectories can provide important insights. Recently, Lagrangian methods have also been used to construct a microphysics scheme (Grabowski and Pawlowska, 2019). In this approach, Lagrangian particles are interpreted as clusters of hydrometeors and are advected by the velocity field provided by the Eulerian model. This way, microphysical processes of collision and coalescence can be better represented than in bulk or microphysics schemes.

Lagrangian methods have also been used in the study of atmospheric dynamics in a variety of scenarios, from the convective boundary layer (Querzoli, 1999; Xuhui Cai, 2006), to cumulus and stratocumulus clouds (Tian and Kuang, 2016; Tian et al., 2019), and also in deep convective regimes (Torri et al., 2015; Torri and Kuang, 2016; Tian and Kuang, 2019). Here, we will discuss and present a detailed evaluation of the Lagrangian Particle Dispersion Model (LPDMX) that has been designed to run online along with an LES/CRM model.

In Section 2, we will present the main features of the LPDMX, describing the evolution equations for the Lagrangian particles and their implementation. In Section 3, we will discuss a series of validation tests to show the performance of the LPDMX. Finally, in Section 4, we will draw some conclusions regarding the Lagrangian model presented here.

2 Eulerian models description

The LPDMX is coded in Fortran 90 and it simulates the motion of a number of Lagrangian particles released in a model atmosphere. The particles are considered massless, but move within parcels of air of a given mass. In order to be successfully applied, the LPDMX needs to be coupled to an LES or a CRM model that provides physical quantities like the velocities that are used to advect Lagrangian particles. In its original version, the LPDMX was coupled with the System for Atmospheric Modeling (SAM; Khairoutdinov and Randall, 2003), version 6.8.2, a model that solves the anelastic equations of motion and uses liquid water static energy and nonprecipitating and precipitating total water as thermodynamic prognostic variables. The equations in SAM are solved with doubly periodic boundary conditions in the horizontal directions. A prognostic turbulent kinetic energy 1.5-order closure scheme is used to parameterize subgrid-scale effects. SAM uses a fully staggered Arakawa C-type grid.

Because SAM only allows for periodic boundary conditions, which could limit the scope of the results that can be achieved with the LPDMX, we have also coupled the Lagrangian model with the Cloud Model 1 (CM1), version 18, a non-hydrostatic, non-linear, fully compressible model (Bryan and Fritsch, 2002). The model integrates the equations of motion in time using a second-order Runge-Kutta scheme, and a fifth-order advection scheme. The model is relatively flexible and allows the user to choose between a variety of turbulence closures, microphysics schemes, and boundary conditions. Although this model comes with the option of simulating Lagrangian particles, these were originally implemented to have to satisfy periodic boundary conditions, which could lead to inconsistencies when the Eulerian model satisfies open-radiation boundary conditions.

2.1 Initialization

In order to run the LPDM, the user first needs to set two parameters: the number of Lagrangian particles that are initialized in each column of the LES/CRM model, $lpdm_num$, and the highest model level that the Lagrangian particles can reach, $lpdm_top$. The latter acts as a rigid lid on which Lagrangian particles are reflected elastically. While having the freedom to set the lid to a level lower than the LES/CRM model top may help save some memory, the reflective boundary conditions could cause Lagrangian particles to accumulate near the lid if this is set to an altitude where convective updrafts or gravity waves are strong.

One of the fundamental assumptions of the LPDMX is that Lagrangian particles are viewed as point entities embedded in parcels of air of a given mass, m . As a first step to achieve this, the $lpdm_num$ Lagrangian particles in each model column are assigned initial positions randomly with a probability distribution which is uniform in the horizontal directions and in the pressure coordinate. With this construction, the mass of a parcel in which a Lagrangian particle is embedded is given by:

$$m = \frac{1}{lpdm_num} \iiint \rho(z) dx dy dz \approx \frac{\Delta x \Delta y}{n_0} \sum_{k=1}^{lpdm_top} \rho_k \Delta z_k, \quad (1)$$

where the integral is taken over a model column, and the approximation represents the numerical implementation of the calculation, with ρ_k and δz_k being respectively the air density and the vertical grid spacing at level k . Apart from $lpdm_num$, all the other quantities involved in Equation 1 are provided by the LES/CRM model.

2.2 The evolution equation

Although the LPDMX is coupled with an LES/CRM model, the coupling is only one way because Lagrangian particles are assumed to be passive elements that do not influence the dynamics of the system in any way. Furthermore, no interaction takes place between two or more Lagrangian particles. Similarly to past studies (Weil et al., 2004; Heus and Jonker, 2008), the position vector of a Lagrangian particle, \mathbf{x} , evolves according to the following equation:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{x}}{dt} = \mathbf{u}_r(\mathbf{x}(t), t) + \mathbf{u}_s(\mathbf{x}(t), t) \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{u}_r(\mathbf{x}(t), t)$ and $\mathbf{u}_s(\mathbf{x}(t), t)$ are respectively the resolved and the sub-grid scale velocity vectors. At every time step, the LPDMX solves this equation for each particle using a second-order Adams-Bashforth advection scheme.

The resolved velocity is given by a linear interpolation along the same direction of the interfacial components given by the LES/CRM model. For instance, if the position of a particle in the x-direction is between the $(i)^{th}$ and $(i+1)^{th}$ interfaces, and if α represents the distance of the particle from the $(i)^{th}$ interface, the x-component of the particle's velocity is given by:

$$90 \quad u_r = \frac{1}{\Delta x} (\alpha U_i + (1 - \alpha) U_{i+1}) \quad (3)$$

where U_i and U_{i+1} are the velocities given by SAM on the i and $i+1$ interfaces. The generalization to the other dimensions is straightforward:

$$v_r = \frac{1}{\Delta y} (\beta V_j + (1 - \beta) V_{j+1}) \quad w_r = \frac{1}{\Delta z_k} (\gamma W_k + (1 - \gamma) W_{k+1}) \quad (4)$$

Although in Lagrangian particle models it is often customary to use a tri-linear interpolation to assign particles velocities (e.g., Bryan and Fritsch, 2002), ours is the only choice compatible with the interpretation of Lagrangian particles as massless entities embedded in air parcels because it satisfies the continuity equation. For instance, let us consider the limiting case in which an infinite number of Lagrangian particles is used and let us consider a generic grid box. The continuity equation in the grid box is given by:

$$\frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \alpha} + \frac{\partial v_r}{\partial \beta} + \frac{\partial w_r}{\partial \gamma} = \left(\frac{U_i - U_{i+1}}{\Delta x} \right) + \left(\frac{V_j - V_{j+1}}{\Delta y} \right) + \left(\frac{W_k - W_{k+1}}{\Delta z_k} \right) = 0, \quad (5)$$

100 where the last equality is enforced by the continuity equation in the LES/CRM.

The second term in the right-hand side of Equation 2, $\mathbf{u}_s(\mathbf{x}(t), t)$, is the sub-grid scale velocity. While we initially parameterized this term in a similar fashion to (Weil et al., 2004), we found that with this approach continuity is violated and Lagrangian particles tend to accumulate near the center of a grid box in the horizontal directions and at the bottom of the model domain. In order to ensure that the Lagrangian particles follow the resolved flow, we followed the approach of other authors (e.g. Gopalakrishnan and Avissar, 2000; Yeo and Romps, 2013) and ignored sub-grid scale velocities.

2.3 Assigning properties and ensuring consistency

One of the advantages of using the LPDMX is that Lagrangian particles can be assigned dynamical or thermodynamic properties, and their histories can be examined to gain a better understanding of the processes that an air parcel experiences in a given window of time. However, because SAM and the LPDMX are distinct models and they use different approaches, it is first necessary to ensure that the two are consistent.

The first step in order to ensure consistency is to verify that mass fluxes computed in SAM and those from the LPDMX are the same. If we consider a set of properties λ , for example to denote cloudy grid boxes, the λ -mass flux at level k determined by SAM is given by:

$$M_e(k, t) = \frac{1}{N_x N_y} \sum_{i,j \in \{\lambda\}} \rho_w(k, t) w(i, j, k, t), \quad (6)$$

115 where N_x and N_y are respectively the number of grid boxes in the x- and y-direction, and $\rho_w(k)$ is the air density interpolated on the vertical interface. From the perspective of the LPDMX, on the other hand, the mass flux is simply given by counting

how many particles cross the interfaces between two λ -grid boxes at time t :

$$M_l(k, t) = \frac{1}{(N_x \Delta_x)(N_y \Delta_y) \Delta t} (\mu^+(k) - \mu^-(k)) \quad (7)$$

where $\mu^+(k)$ and $\mu^-(k)$ are the number of particles crossing a λ -interface at level k going up and down, respectively, and Δt is the time step.

In addition to being embedded in air parcels of a given mass, Lagrangian particles can also be assigned properties, like momentum, potential temperature, θ , or water vapor mixing ratio q_v . Denoting any of these variables as ϕ , at the beginning of the simulation, each particle is assigned the value of the grid box that contains the particle. Denoting by $\hat{\phi}_n$ the value assigned to the n^{th} particle, by construction we have that:

$$\phi(i, j, k) = \frac{\sum_{n \in \{i, j, k\}} \hat{\phi}_n}{\sum_{n \in \{i, j, k\}} 1}, \quad (8)$$

which indicates that the value of ϕ given by SAM in the grid box (i, j, k) equals the average $\hat{\phi}_n$ of the particles inside that grid box. At the following time step, $\hat{\phi}_n$ for each particle can be updated while maintaining consistency with the LES/CRM model. The latter typically solves the equations for ϕ by first computing the advective term and applying higher-order corrections, like a flux limiter (Smolarkiewicz and Grabowski, 1990). Using the updated velocities given by the LES/CRM, the LPDMX computes the new positions for the Lagrangian particles, which only mimics the advective part of the equation for ϕ . Thus, in order to maintain consistency between the two models, we add the higher-order correction terms determined by the finite-volume scheme of the LES/CRM to the Lagrangian particles. In a similar spirit to the finite-volume scheme, in each grid cell we assign to every Lagrangian particle the average value of $\hat{\phi}$ in that grid cell. These steps ensure that the LPDMX replicates the advection of ϕ that is done in SAM. For each grid cell, then, tendencies due to diffusion, microphysics and radiation, are applied uniformly to all the particles contained in the cell.

In addition to thermodynamic properties, Lagrangian particles can also be assigned dynamical properties, such as velocity, which are updated in a similar way to the one described above. In this case, instead of adding microphysical or radiative tendency, we will update the velocities using the forces that Lagrangian particles experience. For example, for the vertical velocity component, w , these forces are the Archimedean buoyancy, B , diagnosed from SAM, and pressure gradient forces. In turn, following Houze (1994), we added code in SAM to separate pressure gradient forces into mechanical, $\partial_z p_m$, and, $\partial_z p_B$, buoyancy-related vertical pressure gradients.

2.4 Open-radiative boundary conditions

Because the LPDMX has to be consistent with the LES/CRM model it is coupled to, the latter dictates what boundary conditions to impose on Lagrangian particles in the latter. In the previous subsections, we have discussed a version of the LPDMX coupled with SAM, a model that has periodic boundary conditions in both horizontal directions. Thus, whenever a Lagrangian particle left the domain from one side, its position was changed, and the particle was re-introduced in the domain from the opposite side.

While this approach allows the investigation of a large number of atmospheric phenomena, there are cases for which periodic boundary conditions may not be adequate. Supercell storms, for example, are systems that can generate large cold pools and whose anvils can extend for hundreds of kilometers (e.g., McDonald, 2019). Simulations of these storms with periodic boundary conditions, and the necessity to use an adequate horizontal resolution, would force one to use an impractically big model domain, with the risk of making the simulation too computationally expensive. To obviate this problem, it is customary to use open-radiative boundary conditions Klemp and Durran (1983).

From the point of view of the LPDMX, the main difference with respect to periodic boundary conditions is that, while Lagrangian particles still leave and re-enter the domain, the two steps are not necessarily consequential and do not happen necessarily at the same time. In order to do this, we introduce the notion of a particle stack, an array where particles that leave the domain are temporarily placed or from which particles are taken when mass enters the model domain. At the beginning of the simulation, during the initialization stage, the stack is defined as an array of particles, and half of its entries are assigned particles IDs. This is done because if the stack was initially empty and the simulation started with an injection of mass in the domain, for example caused by some convergence, continuity of Lagrangian particles would be violated. At the same time, if the stack was initially full of particles and the simulation started with some particle leaving the domain, there would be a problem.

The process of moving a particle that has exited the domain to the stack is relatively straightforward and can be implemented easily. The reverse, on the other hand, requires more care. Because, according to Equation 1, every Lagrangian particle can be associated with a mass, m , one could simply determine how much mass is being introduced in each boundary grid cell at a given time step and, whenever this quantity is equal to m , a particle can be moved from the stack to the model domain. However, in a hypothetical situation of a long simulation with a uniform flow that moves so slowly that the mass of air introduced in each grid box at a given time is always smaller than m , the number of particles in the domain would decrease monotonically until none is left.

To address this problem, we introduce a mass line to keep track of how much air enters or exits the computational domain at every time step. The initial length of the mass line equals the total mass of the particles in the stack, and every particle in the stack is assigned a random position on the mass line. Whenever a particle leaves the domain and is transferred to the stack, its mass is added to the mass line over which the particle is also assigned a random position. Whenever a mass δm of air enters the domain, this quantity is removed from the mass line. If the portion of the line that is removed contains any particle, the latter is sent from the stack to the boundary grid cell where δm of air is being advected.

2.5 Output and Parallelization

The LPDMX outputs data in a binary file at a frequency that can be set by the user as a parameter at the beginning of the simulation. At every output time step, the LPDMX opens the output file and writes the updated positions of the particles at that time as a single 4-byte integer number. For each particle, this number is constructed by merge 3-digit numbers that indicate the x, y, and z indices denoting the grid box in which particle is. For example, if particle is in the grid box $i = 153$, $j = 12$, and

$k = 1$, the integer denoting its position is 153012001. Note that this limits the maximum number of grid boxes in any spatial dimension to 999.

In order to improve computational efficiency, the LPDMX code is parallelizable with a master/slave-type architecture. At the beginning of the simulation, a master node is designated and an array is allocated that contains the the unique ID numbers that denote each particle. In slave nodes, smaller arrays are allocated to receive particles from the master. After initial positions are assigned as described in Section 2.1, each particle is sent to the appropriate slave node. During the simulations, particles positions are updated and particles that leave and enter another subdomain are transferred to the slave node that has been assigned that subdomain.

Because at any given time step particles are divided among different nodes, writing the output presents some challenges. Currently, at every output time step, all the particles are transferred from the slave to the master nodes, they are sorted in ascending order according to their IDs, and their positions are then written in the output file. Among other things, this procedure is the main reasons why a large array containing all the particles was allocated in the mater node. A schematic of this process can be found in Figure 5. This method of writing the output when the code is run in parallel mode introduces two important limitations: first, the particle number cannot be too large because otherwise there would not be sufficient memory on a node to allocate an array that contains all the particles; second, sorting algorithms can be very time consuming and significantly increase the runtime of a particular simulation. We have tried different approaches to address these two problems, but, so far, we have not found a satisfactory one that would not create other types of issues.

2.6 Memory usage and performance

To demonstrate the computational efficiency of this parallelized particle model, we perform benchmark on a small domain with 256 grid boxes in both horizontal directions, and 128 layers in the vertical. The cluster used to test the performance possesses Intel computing unit, and has 128 GB memory per core and 28-32 cores per node. During initialization of the particle model, each grid box has an average of five particles. Statistics are then collected after running 60 time steps. It is shown that 32 and 128 cores give the best performance for a domain of 256x256x128 in size, 64 cores actually compute more slowly than 32 cores, due to the longer communication time between nodes. The speed increases again after the overhead communication time is outweighed by the computing efficiency when changing to 128 cores. Given the hardware infrastructure of the used cluster, distributing tasks to 16x8 gives the best performance among different parallelization configurations. The same conclusion holds for other domain sizes as well. In terms of the storage, if we keep track of the location of each particle, the total storage the particle output takes up about 1.5GB for 60 time steps.

3 Validations

210 3.1 Convective Boundary Layer

We begin to examine the performance of the LPDMX with a relatively simple case of a dry boundary layer growth. The model domain for this simulation measures 64 grid cells in each direction, and a resolution of 25 meters is adopted. The time step is set at 3 seconds. The surface temperature and the surface sensible heat fluxes are set to be constant and homogeneous at 300 K and 80 W m⁻², respectively, and an potential temperature is initialized with a linear profile having a 4 K km⁻¹ increase
215 in the vertical. A bulk microphysics scheme is adopted, and radiation scheme follows that of the CAM model. Subgrid-scale turbulent fluxes are calculated using a 1.5 order closure. Lagrangian particles are uniformly distributed across the domain, with an average number of 10 particles per grid box, and their positions are output every model minute.

In order to test the choice of interpolating velocities using a one-dimensional interpolation, as discussed in Section 2.2, we compared the simulation with two additional sensitivity experiments. These were run with exactly the same parameters and
220 thermodynamic sounding as described above, but evolving the Lagrangian particles' positions using two different methods: in the first, the velocities were not interpolated and were considered constant within a grid box; in the second, a three-dimensional interpolation method was used. In formulae, using a notation similar to that of Equation 3, the latter method implies that the x-component of the particle's velocity is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} u_r(x, y, z) = & \delta x * \delta y * \delta z * U_{i+1, j+1, k+1} + (1 - \delta x) * \delta y * \delta z * U_{i, j+1, k+1} + \delta x * (1 - \delta y) * \delta z * U_{i+1, j, k+1} + \dots \\ & \delta x * \delta y * (1 - \delta z) * U_{i+1, j+1, k} + \delta x * (1 - \delta y) * (1 - \delta z) * U_{i+1, j, k} + (1 - \delta x) * \delta y * (1 - \delta z) * U_{i, j+1, k} + \dots \\ & (1 - \delta x) * (1 - \delta y) * \delta z * U_{i, j, k+1} + (1 - \delta x) * (1 - \delta y) * (1 - \delta z) * U_{i, j, k} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

225 where $\delta x = \alpha/\Delta x$, $\delta y = \beta/\Delta y$, and $\delta z = \gamma/\Delta z$. The other two components follow a similar formula and they are not repeated here for the sake of brevity. The top panels of Figure 1 show the positions of particles in a few grid boxes near the model surface using the three different interpolation methods. The plots show that both the choice of not interpolating and that of using a three-dimensional interpolation of the velocities leads to the creation of relatively large holes that are empty of particles. This would be problematic for the interpretation of particles as being embedded in air parcels of a given mass that we are proposing
230 here. The one-dimensional interpolation, on the other hand, appears to ensure a continuity of particles, as desired.

A more systematic presentation of the results suggested by the top panels is given in the bottom panel, where the curves represent the probability distribution functions of the number of particles in near-surface grid boxes. The blue and the yellow curve refer to the case with no interpolation of velocities and a three-dimensional interpolation. Both appear to be non-normal distributions. The red curve, on the other hand, refers to the case with a one-dimensional interpolation of velocities and appears
235 very similar to a normal distribution, as one would expect.

3.2 A shallow convection case: BOMEX

In this section, we will discuss the ability of the LPDMX to assign thermodynamical and dynamical properties to Lagrangian particles and evolve them consistently. In order to do this, we choose a different case than the one discussed in the previous

section, and examine results from a simulation of the undisturbed phase of the Barbados Oceanographic and Meteorological
 240 Experiment (BOMEX). Soundings from this campaign have been widely used to study shallow cumulus convection (e.g.
 Siebesma and Cuijpers, 1995; a.P. Siebesma, 1998; Siebesma et al., 2003; Lenderink et al., 2004; Heus et al., 2009; Romps
 and Kuang, 2010; Tian and Kuang, 2016).

We ran SAM on a doubly periodic domain measuring $6.4 \times 6.4 \text{ km}^2$ with 128 layers in the vertical direction. The grid
 resolution is 25m in both horizontal and vertical directions. The simulation was first spun up for 3 hours until the cloud
 245 fields reached a statistically steady state. Model statistics are output every 1 s, particle location and 3D snapshots are sampled
 every 4s to save memory storage. A monotonic advection scheme is used for scalars and the subgrid-scale turbulent fluxes are
 determined using a 1.5 order closure scheme. The initial soundings, the large-scale forcing, and surface fluxes of this BOMEX
 case are the same as those used in Siebesma et al. (2003).

In order to test that the LPDMX correctly represents the flow simulated by SAM, we will compare mass and moisture
 250 fluxes predicted by the two models. We begin by defining cloudy updrafts as those grid boxes where the vertical velocity w is
 greater than 1 m s^{-1} and the non-precipitating liquid water mixing ratio, q_n , is greater than 0.01 g kg^{-1} . Then, following the
 discussion in Section 2.3, we compute the cloudy mass flux using the LPDMX and that diagnosed from SAM. The results of
 this comparison are shown in Figure 2, with the LPDMX-reconstructed mass flux shown in red, and the SAM-diagnosed mass
 flux in blue. While not perfect, the two methods show a very good agreement. The discrepancy is greatest near cloud base,
 255 where the influence from sub-cloud layer turbulence is strongest. We attribute the differences to the fact that, while the Eulerian
 mass flux is computed every model second, the Lagrangian one is computed only every 4 seconds. To test this hypothesis, we
 reconstructed the Lagrangian mass flux using data every 20, 40, and 60 seconds. The results are shown by the yellow, purple,
 and green curves in Figure 2.

In a similar fashion, to the above paragraphs, Figure 3 compares the horizontally-averaged flux of total water mixing ratio,
 260 q_t , within cloudy updrafts. Lagrangian particles were assigned a value of q_t at the beginning of the simulation, which was then
 evolved using the methods described in Section 2.3. Figure 3 shows again a good agreement between the fluxes reconstructed
 with SAM and those with the LPDMX, discrepancies being attributed to the frequency with which the positions of Lagrangian
 particles are output.

In addition to the mass flux and thermodynamic properties, Lagrangian particles can also be assigned dynamical properties.
 265 Here, we test this by showing how the LPDMX can be used to reconstruct the vertical momentum budget of cloudy grid boxes.
 First, we select a collection of grid boxes along the x -axis at height z and time $t = xxx$ (YANG: WHAT HEIGHT AND AT
 WHAT TIME IN THE SIMULATION). Then, we tracked the particles in the selected in the grid box back to a certain time, t_0 .
 The vertical velocity of each particle was subsequently initialized with the value of the vertical velocity of the grid box where
 the particle was tracked back to. Finally, each particle's velocity was evolved from t_0 to the current time according to:

$$270 \quad w_i(t) = w_i(t_0) + \int_{t_0}^t F_i(s) ds, \quad (10)$$

where

$$F_i(s) = B_i(s) - \frac{1}{\rho_0} \frac{dp'_i(s)}{dz}, \quad (11)$$

where i is the index of the particle, $B_i(s)$ the Archimedean buoyancy at time s , and $\frac{dp'_i(s)}{dz}$ the pressure gradient force. Finally, the vertical velocity in a given grid box at time t is reconstructed as the mean of the velocities of all the contained Lagrangian particles.

The blue and the red curve in Figure 4 show the vertical velocity across the selected slice at time t diagnosed from SAM (blue curve) and reconstructed using the LPDMX (red). The various panels refer to different time windows used to reconstruct the vertical velocity of the particles. The results show that there is generally a very good agreement between the two methods, and provides further confidence in the LPDMX.

3.3 Uniform wind profile

Finally, in order to test the performance of the LPDMX with open-radiative boundary conditions, in this section we present some results obtained using the Lagrangian model coupled to CM1. Because we are primarily interested in verifying that Lagrangian particles are removed and added to the domain correctly, we choose a simple case of a dry atmosphere with no surface heat flux, no radiative heating, and a zonal wind equal to 5 m s^{-1} at all heights. Free-slip boundary conditions are imposed at the bottom and the top of the domain.

Similarly to Section , the initial potential temperature increases from a value of 300 K at the surface with a lapse rate of 4 K km^{-1} . Grid spacing is set to 50 meters in all directions and time step is 1 second. The domain measures 64 grid cells in the horizontal directions and 16 in the vertical. The simulation is run for 3 model hours.

The LPDMX is initialized with 1,280 particles in each column of CM1, which means that there are 5,242,880 particles in total at the beginning of the simulation. With these settings, each particle is considered as embedded in a parcel of air of mass 0.69 kg.

The panels of Figure 7 show the number of particles at each height (left) and the deviation of the number of particles from the total initial number (right) as functions of time. The plots show that, even though the number of particles undergoes fluctuations, the total number at each level and in the domain remains uniform throughout the simulation. The mean number of particles averaged over the three hours of the run is 5,242,784, less than a 0.002% difference from the initial number.

Finally, the blue curve in Figure 8 shows the distribution of particles within model columns sampled over the last two hours of the simulation. Given that all the model columns are initialized with the same number of particles, we chose to discard the first hour of simulation to ensure that our initialization choice would not affect the distribution. Superimposed to the blue curve, the red curve represents a gaussian that was fitted to the data. A Poisson distribution would have been a more appropriate fit, but at large numbers, such as the ones involved here, the two curves converge. The figure shows a very good agreement.

4 Conclusions

In this short manual, we have described the formulation and implementation of a Lagrangian Particle Dispersion Model (LPDMX), that can be embedded into a LES or CRM to track the flow field. We have provided validations of this model in a convective boundary layer, a typical shallow cumulus field, and a case with open-radiative boundary conditions. Additionally, we have implemented this LPDMX in two different large eddy simulations codes: SAM and CM1. This demonstrates that our designed particle model can be used to study both weakly non-linear as well as fully compressible flows. With this added functionality, LES/CRM can be more versatile in the geophysics research field that involves tracer tracking and labeling, which can further our understanding of atmospheric dynamics to a good extend.

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315 **References**

- The West Coast Thermal Trough: Mesoscale Evolution and Sensitivity to Terrain and Surface Fluxes in: *Monthly Weather Review* Volume 141 Issue 8 (2013), https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/mwre/141/8/mwr-d-12-00305.1.xml?tab_body=fulltext-display, 2013.
- Angevine, W. M., Brioude, J., McKeen, S., Holloway, J. S., Lerner, B. M., Goldstein, A. H., Guha, A., Andrews, A., Nowak, J. B., Evan, S., Fischer, M. L., Gilman, J. B., and Bon, D.: Pollutant transport among California regions, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 320 118, 6750–6763, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jgrd.50490>, <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1002/jgrd.50490>, 2013.
- a.P. Siebesma: Shallow cumulus convection, *Buoyant Convection in Geophysical Flows*, pp. 441–486, 1998.
- Brioude, J., Arnold, D., Stohl, A., Cassiani, M., Morton, D., Seibert, P., Angevine, W., Evan, S., Dingwell, A., Fast, J. D., Easter, R. C., Pisso, I., Burkhardt, J., and Wotawa, G.: The Lagrangian particle dispersion model FLEXPART-WRF version 3.1, *Geoscientific Model Development*, 6, 1889–1904, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-6-1889-2013>, 2013.
- 325 Bryan, G. H. and Fritsch, J. M.: A BENCHMARK SIMULATION FOR TESTING MOIST NONHYDROSTATIC NUMERICAL MODEL FORMULATIONS, 2002.
- Cassiani, M., Stohl, A., Olivié, D., Øyvind Seland, Bethke, I., Pisso, I., and Iversen, T.: The offline Lagrangian particle model FLEXPART-NorESM/CAM (v1): Model description and comparisons with the online NorESM transport scheme and with the reference FLEXPART model, *Geoscientific Model Development*, 9, 4029–4048, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-9-4029-2016>, 2016.
- 330 Emanuel, K., Sundararajan, R., and Williams, J.: Hurricanes and global warming: Results from downscaling IPCC AR4 simulations, *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 89, 347–367, <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-89-3-347>, <https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/bams/89/3/bams-89-3-347.xml>, 2008.
- Flato, G., Marotzke, J., Abiodun, B., Braconnot, P., Chou, S. C., Collins, W., Cox, P., Driouech, F., Emori, S., Eyring, V., Forest, C., Gleckler, P., Guilyardi, E., Jakob, C., Kattsov, V., Reason, C., and Rummukainen, M.: Evaluation of Climate Models In *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis*. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2013.
- 335 Gopalakrishnan, S. G. and Avissar, R.: An LES Study of the Impacts of Land Surface Heterogeneity on Dispersion in the Convective Boundary Layer, *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 57, 352–371, 2000.
- Grabowski, Wojciech W. Hugh Morrison, S.-I. S. G. C. A. P. D. and Pawlowska, H.: Modeling of Cloud Microphysics Can We Do Better?, 340 *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, pp. 655–672, 2019.
- Guichard, F. and Couvreux, F.: A short review of numerical cloud-resolving models, *Tellus A: Dynamic Meteorology and Oceanography*, 69, 2017.
- Heus, T. and Jonker, H. J. J.: Subsiding Shells around Shallow Cumulus Clouds, *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 65, 1003–1018, 2008.
- Heus, T., Jonker, H. J. J., Van den Akker, H. E. a., Griffith, E. J., Koutek, M., and Post, F. H.: A statistical approach to the life cycle analysis 345 of cumulus clouds selected in a virtual reality environment, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 114, D06208, 2009.
- Houze, R. A. J.: *Cloud Dynamics*, vol. 53 of *International Geophysics*, Academic Press, 1994.
- Khairoutdinov, M. F. and Randall, D. a.: Cloud Resolving Modeling of the ARM Summer 1997 IOP: Model Formulation, Results, Uncertainties, and Sensitivities, *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 60, 607–625, 2003.
- Klemp, J. B. and Durran, D. R.: An Upper Boundary Condition Permitting Internal Gravity Wave Radiation in Numerical Mesoscale Models, *Monthly Weather Review*, 111, 430–444, [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(1983\)111<0430:AUBCPI>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1983)111<0430:AUBCPI>2.0.CO;2), [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(1983\)111<0430:AUBCPI>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1983)111<0430:AUBCPI>2.0.CO;2), 1983.
- 350

- Knutson, T. R., Zhang, R., and Horowitz, L. W.: Prospects for a prolonged slowdown in global warming in the early 21st century, *Nature Communications*, 7, 1–12, <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms13676>, www.nature.com/naturecommunications, 2016.
- 355 Lenderink, G., Siebesma, A. P., Cheinet, S., Irons, S., Jones, C. G., Marquet, P., Müller, F., Olmeda, D., Calvo, J., Sánchez, E., and Soares, P. M.: The diurnal cycle of shallow cumulus clouds over land: A single-column model intercomparison study, *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 130, 3339–3364, <https://doi.org/10.1256/qj.03.122>, <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1256/qj.03.122>, 2004.
- Mcdonald, J. M.: An analysis of observed cold pools in VORTEX-SE supercells and quasi-linear convective systems, Master's thesis, Texas Tech University, 2019.
- 360 Pisso, I., Sollum, E., Grythe, H., Kristiansen, N. I., Cassiani, M., Eckhardt, S., Arnold, D., Morton, D., Thompson, R. L., Zwaaftink, C. D. G., Evangelio, N., Sodemann, H., Haimberger, L., Henne, S., Brunner, D., Burkhardt, J. F., Fouilloux, A., Brioude, J., Philipp, A., Seibert, P., and Stohl, A.: The Lagrangian particle dispersion model FLEXPART version 10.4, *Geoscientific Model Development*, 12, 4955–4997, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-4955-2019>, 2019.
- Powers, J. G.: Numerical Prediction of an Antarctic Severe Wind Event with the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) Model, <https://doi.org/10.1175/MWR3459.1>, <http://www.wrf-model.org/index.php>, 2007.
- 365 Querzoli, G.: A lagrangian study of particle dispersion in the unstable boundary layer, *Atmospheric Environment*, 30, 2821–2829, 1999.
- Reithmeier, C. and Sausen, R.: ATTILA: atmospheric tracer transport in a Lagrangian model, *Tellus B: Chemical and Physical Meteorology*, 54, 278–299, <https://doi.org/10.3402/tellusb.v54i3.16666>, 2002.
- Romps, D. M. and Kuang, Z.: Do Undiluted Convective Plumes Exist in the Upper Tropical Troposphere?, *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 67, 468–484, 2010.
- 370 Schwartz, C. S., Romine, G. S., Weisman, M. L., Sobash, R. A., Fossell, K. R., Manning, K. W., and Trier, S. B.: A real-time convection-allowing ensemble prediction system initialized by mesoscale ensemble Kalman filter analyses, *Weather and Forecasting*, 30, 1158–1181, <https://doi.org/10.1175/WAF-D-15-0013.1>, 2015.
- Seneviratne, S. I., Donat, M. G., Pitman, A. J., Knutti, R., and Wilby, R. L.: Allowable CO₂ emissions based on regional and impact-related climate targets, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature16542>, <https://www.nature.com/articles/nature16542>, 2016.
- 375 Sherwood, S. C. and Huber, M.: An adaptability limit to climate change due to heat stress, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0913352107/-/DCSupplemental>, www.pnas.org/cgi/doi/10.1073/pnas.0913352107, 2013.
- Siebesma, a. P. and Cuijpers, J. W. M.: Evaluation of Parametric Assumptions for Shallow Cumulus Convection, [http://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/abs/10.1175/1520-0469\(2003\)112<2819:CO3C0650\(3AEOPAFS3E2.0.CO3B2\)>2.0.CO;2](http://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/abs/10.1175/1520-0469(2003)112<2819:CO3C0650(3AEOPAFS3E2.0.CO3B2)>2.0.CO;2), 1995.
- 380 Siebesma, a. P., Bretherton, C. S., Brown, A., Chlond, A., Cuxart, J., Duynkerke, P. G., Jiang, H., Khairoutdinov, M., Lewellen, D., Moeng, C.-H., Sanchez, E., Stevens, B., and Stevens, D. E.: A Large Eddy Simulation Intercomparison Study of Shallow Cumulus Convection, *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 60, 1201–1219, 2003.
- Skamarock, W., Klemp, J. B., Dudhia, J., Barker, D., and Wang, W.: A Description of the Advanced Research WRF Version 3, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/306154004>, 2008.
- Smolarkiewicz, P. K. and Grabowski, W. W.: The multidimensional positive definite advection transport algorithm: nonoscillatory option, *Journal of Computational Physics*, 86, 355 – 375, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991\(90\)90105-A](https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991(90)90105-A), <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/002199919090105A>, 1990.
- Sokolov, A. P., Stone, P. H., Forest, C. E., Prinn, R., Sarofim, M. C., Webster, M., Paltsev, S., Schlosser, C. A., Kicklighter, D., Dutkiewicz, S., Reilly, J., Wang, C., Felzer, B., Melillo, J. M., and Jacoby, H. D.: Probabilistic forecast for twenty-first-century climate based on uncertain-

- ties in emissions (without policy) and climate parameters, *Journal of Climate*, 22, 5175–5204, <https://doi.org/10.1175/2009JCLI2863.1>,
390 <https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/clim/22/19/2009jcli2863.1.xml>, 2009.
- Spiegelhalter, D., Pearson, M., and Short, I.: *Visualizing Uncertainty About the Future*, <http://science.sciencemag.org/>, 2008.
- Stohl, A. and Trickl, T.: A textbook example of long-range transport: Simultaneous observation of ozone maxima of stratospheric and North American origin in the free troposphere over Europe, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 104, 30445–30462, <https://doi.org/10.1029/1999JD900803>, <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1029/1999JD900803>, 1999.
- 395 Tian, Y. and Kuang, Z.: Dependence of entrainment in shallow cumulus convection on vertical velocity and distance to cloud edge, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 43, 4056–4065, 2016.
- Tian, Y. and Kuang, Z.: Why Does Deep Convection Have Different Sensitivities to Temperature Perturbations in the Lower versus Upper Troposphere?, *Journal Of The Atmospheric Sciences*, 76, 27–40, 2019.
- Tian, Y., Z. K., Singh, M. S., and Nie, J.: The Vertical Momentum Budget of Shallow Cumulus Convection: Insights From a Lagrangian
400 Perspective, *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 2019.
- Torri, G. and Kuang, Z.: A Lagrangian Study of Precipitation-Driven Downdrafts, *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 73, 839–853, 2016.
- Torri, G., Kuang, Z., and Tian, Y.: Mechanisms for convection triggering by cold pools, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 42, 1943–1950, 2015.
- Weil, J. C., Sullivan, P. P., Moeng, C.-H., Weil, J. C., Sullivan, P. P., and Moeng, C.-H.: The Use of Large-Eddy Simulations in Lagrangian Particle Dispersion Models, *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 61, 2877–2887, 2004.
- 405 Wohltmann, I. and Rex, M.: The Lagrangian chemistry and transport model ATLAS: validation of advective transport and mixing, *Geoscientific Model Development*, 2, 153–173, 2009.
- Wuebbles, D., Fahey, D. W., and Hibbard, K. A.: How will climate change affect the United States in decades to come?, *Eos*, 99, 18–23, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2017eo086015>, 2018.
- Xuhui Cai, R. Z. . Y. L.: A Large-Eddy Simulation and Lagrangian Stochastic Study of Heavy Particle Dispersion in the Convective Boundary
410 Layer, *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*, 120, 413–435, 2006.
- Yeo, K. and Romps, D. M.: Measurement of Convective Entrainment Using Lagrangian Particles, *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 70, 266–277, 2013.
- Ziegler, L.: A Diabatic Lagrangian Technique for the Analysis of Convective Storms. Part II: Application to a Radar-Observed Storm, *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 30, 2266–2280, 2013.
- 415 Ádám Leelóssy, Mészáros, R., Kovács, A., Lagzi, I., and Kovács, T.: Numerical simulations of atmospheric dispersion of iodine-131 by different models, *PLOS ONE*, 12, e0172312, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0172312>, <https://dx.plos.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0172312>, 2017.

Figure 1. Particle location distribution corresponding to different interpolation methods

Figure 2. Cloudy updraft mass flux as a function of height. Solid line: Eulerian statistics; circles: Lagrangian statistics.

Figure 3. Cloudy updraft q_t flux as a function of height. Solid line: Eulerian statistics; circles: Lagrangian statistics.

Figure 4. Cloudy updraft vertical velocity along a slice in the x direction with y being fixed when tracking backward in time from 100 s to 800 s. Horizontal axis shows the x location and vertical axis shows the reconstructed vertical velocity, and the values are averaged over time over all particles within each grid box. Blue line: Eulerian statistics; green: Lagrangian statistics.

Figure 5. Schematic of LPDM parallelization process

Figure 6. Performance of parallelized LPDM model

Figure 7. Total number of particles at each model level (a) and deviations of total particles from the initial particles in the domain (b) as a function of time for the uniform-velocity simulation.

Figure 8. Probability distribution function of particles (blue) in the uniform-velocity simulation compared with a gaussian distribution that was fitted to the data.